

DDC Variables for AR4

	DDC-Variable	PCMDI-Variables	Table/ Nr
core data	2m surface air temperature	tas	A1a/3
	2m mean min. air temperature	tasmin	A1f/5
	2m mean max. air temperature	tasmax	A1f/6
	total precipitation	pr	A1a/2
	total incident solar radiation	Rrsds	A1a/13
	mean scalar wind speed	uas/vas	A1a/26+27
	humidity	huss	A1a/28
	mean sea level pressure	psl	A1a /1
	global mean sea level change (th. exp.)	zostoga	O1c/2
extreme Indices	frost days	fd	A4/1
	extreme temperature range	etr	A4/2
	growing season length	gsl	A4/3
	heat wave duration	hwdi	A4/4
	fraction of time (90 th percentile min temp)	tn90	A4/5
	rain > 10 mm/d	r10	A4/6
	consecutive dry days	cdd	A4/7
	max. 5day precipitation	r5d	A4/8
	simple daily intensity index	sdii	A4/9
	fraction of annual total prec. > 95 th percentile	r95t	A4/10
optional data	daily mean temperature variance		
	daily precipitation variance		
	surface skin temperature/SST	ts	A1a/15
	soil moisture (content)	mrso	A1a/5
	large scale precipitation		
	convective precipitation	prc	A1a/18
	snow cover	snc	A1a/24
	snow melt	snm	A1a/25
	snow depth	snd	A1a/8
	850 hPa height	zg	A1c/7
	500 hPa height	zg	A1c/7
	200 hPa height	zg	A1c/7
	850 hPa height variance		
	500 hPa height variance		
	200 hPa height variance		
	850 hPa temperature	ta	A1c/2
	500 hPa temperature	ta	A1c/2
	200 hPa temperature	ta	A1c/2
	850 hPa rel. humidity	husr	A1c/8
	500 hPa rel. humidity	husr	A1c/8
	200 hPa rel. humidity	husr	A1c/8
	850 hPa u-wind	ua	A1c/3
	500 hPa u-wind	ua	A1c/3
	200hPa u-wind	ua	A1c/3
	850 hPa v-wind	va	A1c/4
	500 hPa v-wind	va	A1c/4
	200 hPa v-wind	va	A1c/4
	Land-sea mask	sftlf	A1b/2
	Land ice area fraction	stfgif	A1b/3
	model gridbox elevation	orog	A1b/1